
AN ASSESSMENT OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN THE MODERN ERA: THE CASE STUDY OF PAKISTAN

Raheela (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7615-1505)

Ph.D. Research Scholar, School of Law, University of Karachi.

Liaquat Ali Abro (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2499-0796)

Law Officer, Law Parliamentary Affairs & Criminal Prosecution Department, Govt. of Sindh.

ABSTRACT

Many different perspectives on human society's evolution may be found in literature from all corners of the globe. Both sexes have been thrust into the spotlight thanks to the distribution as well as existence of race groups and or the progress made therein; on the one hand, men have been portrayed as primarily responsible for development, while on the other, women have been portrayed as being neglected & deprived. Empowerment of women has become a major topic of discussion at international conferences, and it remains an important and pressing problem. For instance, women still make up a disproportionately large share of the world's illiterate population (roughly 67%). Despite being a global phenomenon, gender inequality is more pronounced in countries engaged with nondemocratic governments, and it is likely one of the most disturbing aspects of many contemporary societies. It is the most tragic aspect of human progress that a large percentage of the world's population women live in constant fear of going hungry and in abject poverty due to their subjugation, marginalization, and systematic disempowerment. But in recent decades, as a result of women's awakening, women have redefined their roles from traditional subordinate, dependent, as well as childbearing women to present empowered women.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Modernization, Development, Gender Inequality.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7525882](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525882)